

Thermal, IR and XRD Studies of Ammonium-interacted Deolite

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COMMERCIAL deolite is a desiccant having similar properties as 4A type zeolites. To our knowledge commercial deolite has never been used for cation-exchange or adsorption. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to use deolite as a cation-exchanger for ion like $\text{NH}_4^+(\text{I})$, and the new material has been used as an adsorbent for ammonia with a view to testing its potential for pollution control. Effect of heating up to 900° has been followed by TG analysis and ir spectroscopy. X-ray diffraction studies of the NH_4^+ -deolite and its adsorbed derivatives provide useful information on their structure as compared with those of 4A zeolites¹.

Experimental

Deolite sample (Ras Enterprises) was immersed in a saturated aqueous ammonium chloride for several days and later eluted with fresh lots of the same solution. It was then filtered and air-dried to a white exchanged sample of deolite. The sample was stored with liquor ammonia in a refrigerator.

The NH_4^+ -deolite and its adsorbed samples were subjected to TG analysis upto 900° at a heating rate of $15^\circ \text{ min}^{-1}$ using a Perkin-Elmer thermobalance. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded² on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. X-Ray diffractograms were obtained between 2θ angles of 7° and 60° using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation of 1.5418 \AA on a Phillips PW 1140 instrument. Most of the reflections were indexed for (hkl) value following reported methods³.

Results and Discussion

Deolite shows a remarkable exchange capacity with NH_4^+ ion which replaced 80.71% of Na_2O . Such type of work was carried out by earlier workers with other zeolites.

Total weight-loss in TG analysis of NH_4^+ -exchanged deolite has been found to be 23.40%. The thermogram consists of two weight-loss steps. The first in the temperature range $60-378^\circ$ with a weight-loss of 18.50% which can be attributed due to the loss of water. Partial deammoniation is also a distinct possibility as two DTG endotherms are absorbed successively around 105° and at $300-350^\circ$. The weight-loss of NH_4^+ -deolite is slightly higher than the other exchanged forms and also deolite and this extra loss can be due to deammoniation. The second weight-loss (4.90%) located beyond this temperature range, can be attributed to the breaking of OH groups or dehydroxy-

lation. Thus dehydration, deammoniation and dehydroxylation processes have been observed during thermal treatment of this derivative. A white residue was also obtained after thermal treatment and this shows same characteristic properties, which evolves ammonia and leaves a hydrogen on the framework as hydroxyl group. It has been suggested that protons are initially formed but these rearrange and form hydroxyl group⁴.

IR spectra of deolite show no remarkable change for major structural vibrations. The absorption band due to Si-O lies at 1000 cm^{-1} as a broad band. NH_3 -adsorbed samples show the presence of two volatile cations and a high degree of adsorption. Peaks in the region of 650 and 420 cm^{-1} are assigned to symmetric T-O stretching and T-O bendings. On heating, the peaks at 1645 and 1400 cm^{-1} disappeared, supporting the fact that dehydration and deammoniation occurred but the framework structure of deolite remains unaltered.

From the X-ray data it is clear that no major change has taken place after cation-exchange and crystallinity of deolite still remained unaffected, but the residue shows some interesting characteristics. This derivative appears to lose its crystallinity and becomes amorphous.

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